

The architecture of land degradation early warning based on Earth observation

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Abstract—Early detection and prevention of natural and anthropogenic degradation processes are especially relevant. This paper proposes a suitable architecture of a cloud-based early warning system for assessing land degradation based on satellite Earth observation and other necessary geospatial data. The early warning system is based on efficient methods for the time series of land degradation indicators fusion and algorithms for land degradation risk assessment. Earth observation data includes multispectral and radar satellite imagery and derived data products. Ground-truth data construct auxiliary data in concert with topographic, geoclimatic, cadastral, socioeconomic, and other statistical data. The use of the ArcGIS Online Portal is suggested for the processing of heterogeneous geospatial data. As a result, the authors intend to build a general knowledge-based model for assessing and predicting land degradation.

Keywords—distributed data processing architecture, heterogeneous geospatial data, geoinformation technology, Earth observation, satellite data product, early warning, land degradation

I. INTRODUCTION

Land degradation (LD) is the gradual deterioration of the soil's physical, chemical and biological properties, a decrease in fertility and bioproductivity caused by natural and/or anthropogenic causes, mainly climate change, wildfires, unsustainable land use and mining [1]. At present, LD is observed in almost all geoclimatic zones of the Earth [2]. In regions of extensive agriculture, LD leads to decreased agricultural land productivity and economic value, food insecurity, and negative socioeconomic consequences. Approximately 40% of our planet's land has already been degraded, affecting half of humanity in world GDP terms. If nothing changes, by 2050, there will be a threat to people's food security [3]. Climatic changes occur unevenly in space, which is determined by the physiographic features of the region under consideration. In particular, such unevenness is inherent in Europe and its adjoining territories [4].

The main hypothesis of the newly opened HORIZON-MSCA-2021-SE-01-01 “Earth Observation for Early Warning of Land Degradation at the European Frontier” (EWALD) international research project (<https://ewald-ecommco.hub.arcgis.com/>) is the fundamental possibility of observing and studying future processes of land degradation in regions close to Europe, where climate change and anthropogenic pressures occur more strongly. Such regions are called the European Frontier in the project. Within the European Frontier, test sites were selected to study land degradation, particularly natural-caused – in Morocco and anthropogenic-induced – in Ukraine.

Modern geoinformation technologies that use long-term series of satellite Earth observation (EO), cartographic and other geospatial data and ground-truth measurements have been chosen as the main tool for LD investigation within the European Frontier. However, even though pure ground-based measurements more fully and reliably characterise LD, they do not scale well over a wide area and lose the generalisation effect, which is very important in the study of long-term processes of a regional scale [5]. Satellite EO is spared this drawback; it provides high repeatability of measurements and is easy for automatic processing. Therefore, remote sensing methods, especially satellite EO, are extremely important for LD mapping, assessment and forecasting, and their viability has been proven in many efforts [6, 7].

Land degradation is one of the large-scale complex hazardous processes in geospheres, and which early warning (EW) concept is extremely useful for negative impact prevention or mitigation [8]. However, implementing a near-automatic system for collecting, processing, and analysing multi-time multiscale multichannel satellite images and other heterogeneous geospatial data is challenging [9]. In known papers, the architecture of similar systems is either described too generally [10] or based on ground data only [11]. The involvement of land cover spatial patterns as one of the EW

signals seems promising [12], although other possible indicators of LD vulnerability exist and should be analysed too [13].

Therefore, this work aims to propose a suitable architecture of a cloud-based EW system for land degradation based on satellite EO and other necessary geospatial data.

This paper is organised in a following manner: Section 2 summarises the main models and methods for land degradation within the proposed architecture framework. Section 3 describes the capabilities of available geospatial tools planned for the proposed architecture implementation. Section 4 provides a functional diagram of the general architecture for early warning of land degradation and briefly describes the main blocks. Finally, the concise conclusions and references are listed at the end of the paper.

II. MODELS AND METHODS

Land degradation is a complex, internally interrelated, naturally and anthropogenically determined phenomenon that has been studied by science and implemented in practice for a long time [14]. The general scientific approach to detecting and mapping land degradation involves understanding the ecosystem processes that lead to LD and evolving the key drivers that determine it.

A. Drivers and indicators

LD drivers are usually subdivided into natural and socioeconomic, as listed in Table 1 [15].

TABLE I. MAIN DRIVERS OF LAND DEGRADATION

<i>Natural drivers</i>	<i>Socio-economic drivers</i>
Climate	Population density
Topography	Unsustainable land management
Land cover	Infrastructure development
Vegetation condition	Land tenure
Soil erodibility	Market access
	Poverty

The next step is to determine the LD indicators, i.e. useful information entities that can be extracted from Earth observations and auxiliary geospatial data according to the already agreed LD drivers [16].

As LD spectral indicators are commonly referred the normalised difference vegetation index (NDVI) [17] and one's regression-depended values – vegetation cover fraction (VCF), the green vegetation amount – leaf area index (LAI) [18], productivity indicators – a fraction of absorbed photosynthetically active radiation (FAPAR) and net primary production (NPP) [19], as well as water/temperature indicators – normalised difference water index (NDWI), normalised difference snow index (NDSI), temperature condition index (TCI) and vegetation health index (VHI) [20]. Soil salinisation is manifested by different spectral salinisation indices [21]. Important indicators of LD are the land cover or land use classification [22] and the spatial distribution of soil erosion, obtained, as a rule, using geospatial modelling [23]. Highly useful LD indicators, mainly for open soils and tree vegetation,

can be ensured by radar satellite imagery, especially multi-polarisation and interferometric [24]. Besides, radar interferometry is capable of acquiring and regularly updating the precision digital elevation model (DEM) [25], which provides a direct evaluation of the “Topography” driver from Table 1.

B. Probabilistic model

Since the quantitative assessment of the LD risk is inherently related to changes occurring on the land surface and in ecosystems, this assessment should be based on determined indicators change analysis over time [26]. The complexity of models, the diversity of entities and the ambiguity of the key relationships inside landscapes under study lead to the rationality of an evidence-based framework engagement to assess the LD risk [27]. The problem of simultaneously stacking the influence of several heterogeneous, often contradictory, drivers and their time series seems quite complicated. For this purpose, evidence theory [28], Bayesian approach [29], fuzzy inference [30], deep learning [31], etc. can be applied.

C. Time series fusion

Since land degradation is a complex spatiotemporal process, one's analysis requires systematic measurements and observations of physical, geochemical, atmospheric and some other parameters of the natural environment. Such parameters, i.e., land surface condition indicators, are used for land degradation assessment and prediction. However, the natural environment parameters involved as indicators can be measured in different physical values and scales (quantitative, ordinal, nominal, other), have different accuracy, data format, etc. The indicators heterogeneity is a serious problem for combining and analysing them conjointly. The solution is mapping the value range of each indicator into a probability domain.

To assess land degradation within the study area, assuming that the operator for mapping the F_n value range of the Q_n indicator into the p_n probability of LD vulnerability is known:

$$F_n: Q_n \rightarrow p_n \in [0, 1], n = 1, 2, \dots, n \quad (1)$$

An analytical or graphical relationship for the such operator can be obtained, in particular, by statistical compilation [32], geosystem simulation [33, 34] or expert evidence [35]. Then, using the measured/observed values of the indicators involved, the LD probabilities p_n are determined, and later these probabilities are fused into combined probability P according to the Bayes rule [36, 37].

D. Risk assessment

Each term of series (1) indicates the probability of degradation within the study area at the corresponding timepoint, but in practicalities, as a rule, probabilistic estimation itself is not enough. Instead, the risk category is more informative for situation awareness. The risk concept is interpreted in different ways [38–40], but for our case, the risk value assessment requires not only the probability of

degradation but also the quantitative performance, e.g. level or consequences, of this event. A similar approach was applied, for example, in [41].

Because of the previous, the most appropriate equation for the risk $R(t)$ assessment of study area degradation at timepoint t will be

$$R(t) = f(|S(t) - S_{ref}|) \cdot u(t) \quad (2)$$

where $S(t)$ is the study area state at timepoint t , S_{ref} is the study area reference state, $f(\cdot)$ is the normalised positive nondecreasing function, $0 \leq |f| \leq 1$, $u(t)$ is the level of uncertainty of reaching the $S(t)$ state.

The reference state of the study area is understood as its state with a minimum degradation hazard, in other words, the most favourable state. This state is characterised by a set of indicators with known values. The level of uncertainty $u(t)$ associated with the state $S(t)$ can be expressed by the combined probability P introduced above if the Bayesian approach is used or through the mass of belief if evidence theory is used [42].

III. GEOSPATIAL TOOLS

Enterprise | Client/Server vs Web (EWS Prototype on ArcGIS Online) Platform has three deployment levels. The lowest level is for ArcGIS Analysts. Its call the “System of Record” and is used for preparing, organising and managing the geographic context. This system is built for capturing feature content using transactional workflows to produce authoritative, well-structured information (Web Portal services) provided for use on the second and third levels. Types of content can be Imageries, Tables, Vector data, 3D, Real-Time Data, Big Data, Lidar, Unstructured data, BIM and more.

The middle level is (Web cloud GIS Portal) for ArcGIS administrators. Its call the “System of Insight” and is used for storing, creating and administering the structure of access to services and applications, organising multiuser work with data, and providing spatial analytics tools for creating custom applications.

The upper level is for ArcGIS users (Desktop, Web Browser or Mobile). Its call the “System of Engagement” and is used for GIS consumers to work with geospatial content on any device, place and time.

A functional diagram of the general architecture of the ArcGIS Platform is presented in Fig. 1.

A. ArcGIS Desktop, Server, GDB

ArcGIS Pro is the new version of the desktop GIS application in the ArcGIS ESRI software line. As a 64-bit application, it takes many new capabilities compared with ArcMap Desktop. ArcGIS Pro supports all types of functionalities as the last version of ArcMap Desktop: collecting data from many sources, visualisation of them on the screen of a device that is used; storage data in Geo Data Base (GDB); tools set for extraction feathers on the area of interest; a huge toolset for data geoprocessing and all this capability

work at the same time in 2D and 3D spaces. It is possible to share geoinformation as services in ArcGIS Online and ArcGIS Enterprise Portal too. This guarantee alone Web-window for common users work through the Web.

Figure 1. Functional diagram of the general architecture of the ArcGIS Platform

ArcGIS Server is the server software component in ArcGIS Enterprise ESRI software line that makes somebody's geo dates available to other users via intranet and Internet. That is achieved through GIS services, which allow the server machine to work with all user device requests actively.

ArcGIS GDB is a storage of geographic datasets in many types of formats and coordinates systems that we load in a common file system folder. It can be deployed as a multiuser relational database management system (MRDMS). The MRDMS can be used as an IBM Db2, Microsoft SQL Server, Oracle, PostgreSQL, to SAP HANA. The number of GDB customers may vary from only one to a group of enterprises or for all country citizens.

B. ArcGIS Online Platform

ArcGIS Online is a secured, reliable geographic information system (GIS) delivered using the software-as-a-service (SaaS) model. ArcGIS Online services are elastic, available on demand, managed by ESRI, and accessed by a client running on a wide range of options. It protects safe work for all users.

An ArcGIS Online HUB (website) is a set of Web pages that share for customers with a single domain name. The website can be created for working groups, organisations, or the whole country to cover relevant work topics. ArcGIS Portal can be used as an alone Web site or be a part of ArcGIS Online HUB. The functional diagram of the ArcGIS Portal (Online) is presented in Fig. 2.

An ArcGIS Portal (Online) provide a wide set of Data, Applications, Maps and Geoprocessing capabilities via web pages from many or at least one web server machine.

The technology workflow of the ArcGIS Online working is presented in Fig. 3.

Figure 2. Block diagram of the ArcGIS Online Portal

ArcGIS Hub reunites the working process for everyone who used geolocation as a “science of where”. It reunites organisations, governments, countries, and continents and engages them in work in a handy platform with a geospatial environment. Furthermore, it gives them a friendly, intuitive understanding interface for a quick start to working with people with any level of geospatial knowledge.

Figure 3. Technology workflow of the ArcGIS Online working

ArcGIS Hub allows users to leverage geospatial data and all related documents, geoprocessing workflow and widgets, and create their groups and maps themes.

Users can access an ArcGIS Hub resource via subscriptions to ArcGIS Online and organise all settings they need: count of members with their rights, count of customers group, design of site and pages.

For most site-creating/editing workflows, users will use the site's side panel. This panel includes the Settings, Header, Theme, Layout and Footer menus. A prototype of the EWALD project site is presented in Fig. 4.

Figure 4. The screenshot was taken on 14 March 2023 of the homepage EWALD project site

ArcGIS Portal Applications. The main used applications in ArcGIS Portal Apps are Operations Dashboard for ArcGIS, ArcGIS StoryMaps, Experience Builder, Web AppBuilder or Configurable Apps.

Operations Dashboard for ArcGIS is a web-based application. This application is usually used for organising process dispatching. In addition, it gives powerful tools for monitoring many indexes in time and space.

Operations Dashboard for ArcGIS easy for setting from ready to use pattern. Users can fast configure an application with all charts, gauges, maps, and other visual and ranged elements needed for reflecting events or processes in near real-time. Users have all information that they need in one monitor window. The indicators change information in depends on that update.

It is the best way to provide dynamic information about any process. An example of the Operation Dashboard Panel is presented in Fig. 5.

Figure 5. Example of Functional Operations Dashboard for ArcGIS for climate monitoring

ArcGIS Story Maps is a distribution creation web application that allows users to distribute their text maps in the presence of multiple media resources. Used for: create a story with a constructor. Map stories and descriptions, text descriptions, lists, images, videos, embedded elements, and other media resources; publish and share a story. Each published story has its URL to share the story within limits selected by the group or globally, create and publish collections. Collections of historical records and ArcGIS web applications will be bundled together, making them easier to present and share and manage stories. View and edit stories on the Stories page, search for the stories of other organisation members, and add favourites to the favourites list.

ArcGIS Experience Builder is ArcGIS Portal Application providing ready-to-use templates for creating users' own customers' applications. It has a reach set of ready-to-use: content, widgets, services, and background maps that work with 2D and 3D data.

Both of them can be used for application creation without coding. In addition, a ready-to-use application is available for displaying and analysing data on any device (including a mobile device) without writing program code.

Set of Mobile Field applications. Survey123, ArcGIS QuickCapture, and ArcGIS Field Maps are the leading used Mobile Field applications.

Survey123 is a data collection software — a tool for creating, filling out and analysing data collection forms. With Survey123, users can create forms with questions, the answers to which will be collected as geospatial data. Forms can be designed to collect different data types, such as text, numeric, photos, and geospatial coordinates. Survey123 allows users to use different types of questions. In addition, users can

customise data collection forms according to their needs and requirements.

The acquired data can be analysed and displayed on a map using ESRI ArcGIS Online's integrated features and exported to various formats, including CSV and Excel, for further use and processing. In addition, to allow data collection anytime and anywhere, one can use the ArcGIS Survey123 application, which could work as a stand-alone application or web browser on mobile devices, laptops or desktops. All data were collected in the ArcGIS platform.

The fastest way to collect field data is ArcGIS QuickCapture. With this application, users can quickly record field measurements from a moving vehicle during a site survey, aerial survey, or damage assessment. The basic idea behind QuickCapture is to allow users to collect data quickly by simply pressing a button on the screen of their mobile device. With the app, the user can configure buttons on the screen that provide a specific list of actions, such as capturing coordinates, taking photos and videos, and entering text or numbers. QuickCapture also allows setting up rules for data collection, which allows automatically filling in fields with data from other sources, including databases and geospatial data services.

The application is a powerful tool that allows data collection quickly and efficiently, significantly increasing productivity and work efficiency.

ArcGIS Field Maps is a mobile application that combines data collection, map viewing, and location capabilities into one application. Working with multiple mobile applications creates challenges for employees, as they need to download and log in to each application separately, download multiple copies of map data for offline work, and switch between multiple applications to complete workflows. ArcGIS Field Maps allows users to download, sign in and work with just one application, saving space on mobile devices by eliminating the need to duplicate data (e.g., base maps across multiple applications). Field Maps: combines simple map and label viewing; collection and verification of highly accurate field data; work planning and task management; and step-by-step navigation. Location tracking lets supervisors know where their employees are and where they have been. Mobile workers can also view their routes and track themselves in the field.

Availability of training. There are many ESRI software training courses and programs available for free. Some are good, and some are not, but the best ones are those created by theorists and practitioners of a particular field. Professionals who study and research GIS technologies in theory and apply them in their daily work can share their experiences with others.

ESRI's software training courses provide these opportunities: grow user skills, productivity, and confidence; ensure sustainable GIS workflows and operations; expand the use of ArcGIS maps and applications across the organisation; communicate the strategic impact of the GIS program and workforce.

GIS courses have been designed with several audiences in mind. Two formats are commonly used to teach GIS technologies: online and traditional classroom learning. Each

of them has advantages and disadvantages. Everyone can choose the training format, time, place, etc., which will give them better knowledge.

IV. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

Therefore, it is possible to distinguish two main data sources in the proposed system. These are Earth observation data and ground-truth ones. EO data include level 1 multispectral and radar satellite imagery, level 2 satellite data products based on the former and level 3 simulation outputs of phenomena and processes on the land surface [43]. On the other hand, ground-truth data and topographic, geoclimatic, cadastral, socioeconomic and other statistical data construct auxiliary data.

Nowadays, a huge amount of EO data is available, and almost all low- and medium-resolution satellite images and products are distributed free of charge. The main sources of EO data are major space agencies, such as NASA and ESA, and national or international EO-oriented organisations, such as USGS, NOAA, Copernicus, and others [44]. The last ones, as a rule, have several centres for primary and thematic data processing in their structure, as well as geoportals for searching and accessing data [45]. Data processing from various Earth observation satellite missions of different spectral, spatial and temporal resolutions is carried out more or less consistently, at least for levels 1 and 2 products. That allows the development of distributed EO data processing systems, thereby improving satellite imaging control, coverage, and revisit time [46]. Distributed processing of EO data is especially highly-demanded in the face of commissioning the high-end satellite imaging constellations of dozens and hundreds of small and microsatsellites [47].

After that, we get a concept of a possible architecture for early warning of land degradation. Finally, a functional diagram of such architecture is presented in Fig. 6.

Figure 6. Functional diagram of the general architecture for early warning of land degradation

Interaction with data providers and users is carried out through the corresponding connectors. The EO data connector by ordinary is established as automatic, using the appropriate APIs of data providers. Ground-truth and user connectors must have a GUI, usually through a web browser. It may be necessary to arrange additional connectors for required census

and statistical data from the relevant databases of local authorities within the study area.

After passing through the EO connector, a task-oriented EO engine processes the remotely sensed data and converts it into unified regularised data products. The heterogeneity of the input EO data implies flexibility and wide-range adjustability of the EO processing engine [48].

The EO data products obtained from the EO engine are stacked into the time series of LD indicators. All available auxiliary data are co-registered synchronously with the backbone time series of EO data. The LD indicators' time series and auxiliary data are stored in aggregate in the system's data warehouse, which is worth collating in the cloud [49].

A knowledge-based model for land degradation assessment and prediction takes on the role of the core of the architecture being developed. The model contains all required equations and algorithms for estimating, predicting and raster mapping the land degradation risk. The time series analysis from the data warehouse is performed pixel-wise, taking into account both the time background and local spatial vicinity. When a new data chunk is entered, time series and forecasts are recomputed automatically, and the resulting maps are updated.

The mapping engine, designed as a generic web mapping service [50], is intended for web-based visualisation of the proposed architecture's outputs and interactive user interaction.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The problem of land fertility loss and wide desertification areas, especially in African countries, is well known and, unfortunately, is only exacerbated. However, at the same time, the land degradation dynamics are also enhanced in a number of countries of the European continent. In this regard, the timely identification of hidden, latent threats to land resources by developing a system for early detection and prevention of degradation processes is becoming highly relevant and globalised.

This paper proposes the general architecture of the system for early warning of land degradation based on the joint analysis of Earth observation data and ground-truth ones. EO data includes multispectral and radar satellite imagery and derived data products. In concert with topographic, geoclimatic, cadastral, socioeconomic and other statistical data, ground-truth data construct auxiliary data.

The ArcGIS Platform is used for heterogeneous geospatial data processing. The advantages of this platform are the 2D, 3D, and 4D data support, the availability of a ArcGIS solutions and applications variety, and the users' opportunity to work across the ArcGIS system through Web GIS and many others. The structure of ArcGIS Online Portal and the Technology workflow of the ArcGIS Online working are proposed and briefly described.

The authors intend for future works to develop efficient methods for the time series of LD indicators fusion and algorithms for LD risk assessment under partial uncertainty, as well as build a general knowledge-based model for land degradation assessment and prediction.

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